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The Sino-Russian relationship and its implications across the Eurasian and Indo-Pacific strategic theaters

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ABSTRACT Viewing Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific region as distinct strategic theaters is no longer viable. Russia and China are increasingly aligning across both regions, challenging the Western-led liberal international order and its associated security architecture. We begin by examining China's relations in Central Asia as a case study of Eurasian geopolitical transformation and its implications for Sino-Russian relations. China has become increasingly important in the region's economic and security spheres. Although Beijing and Moscow are not overtly competing in Central Asia, their relationship is not without friction. Nevertheless, tensions have gradually eased amid expanding Sino-Russian interactions and Russia's growing reliance on China following its international isolation and sanctions in 2022. We further argue that China plays a significant role in shaping Russia's engagement with the Asia-Pacific, influencing both its global positioning and national identity. While Russia's regional policies are not solely shaped by its ties with Beijing, its increasing dependence on China and, more recently, North Korea, has become more pronounced since 2022. We then compare how states across Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific navigate intensifying great power rivalry, offering key insights into the future evolution of the international order and security architectures. Despite the impact of the 2022 Russo-Ukrainian war, both Central Asian and Southeast Asian countries continue to pursue diversified external relations. Russia and China remain central to the multivector policies of Central Asian states, while China and the US exert significant influence over the strategic choices of Asia-Pacific countries, even during the early stages of Trump's second administration.

KEYWORDS Sino-Russian Relations, Eurasia, Indo-Pacific, Central Asia, International Order

Viewing Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific as separate strategic theaters is no longer viable. Russia and China are increasingly coordinating across both regions, a trend reinforced by Russia's 2022 attack on Ukraine. This development reflects decades of evolving foreign-policy thinking in Moscow and Beijing—thinking deeply rooted in each country's historical self-perception, national identity, and national interests

(Rozman 2025; Neumann 2017; Callahan 2010; Hopf 2002, Zhao 2004). Although the Eurasian and Asia-Pacific regions once constituted largely distinct arenas for Russian and Chinese engagement, the two powers have gradually shifted from regional compartmentalization toward a mutually reinforcing pattern of cross-theater coordination.

A substantial body of literature examines Russia's and China's respective interests in Eurasia and the Asia-Pacific (e.g., Trenin 2003; Karaganov and Makarov 2015; Medcalf 2020; Shambaugh 2022; Kang 2023/4; Ghiasy, Chen, and Panda 2025). To begin with the Eurasian space. Geographically, it includes the Caucasus (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia) and Greater Central Asia (Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Mongolia, and Afghanistan; the space remains Russia's primary arena for competition and cooperation with regional actors. Iver Neumann's (2017) analysis of Europe as Russia's constitutive "Other" helps explain the Greater Eurasia concept as a rejection of Westernizing impulses. This identity construction enables Russia to frame itself as a Euro-Pacific power whose great-power status does not depend on Western recognition (Wishnick 2017).

Russian strategic thought has long been shaped by competing geographical visions. Aleksandr Dugin and Dmitri Trenin represent distinct strands of Eurasianism (Guerra 2024) that differ in emphasis but share a focus on Russia's central role in Eurasia, paying comparatively little attention to the relationship between Eurasia and the Asia-Pacific (Dunlop 2001; Shekhovtsov and Umland 2009). By contrast, Yevgeny Primakov and Sergei Karaganov sought to conceptualize the Eurasian and Asia-Pacific spaces as more integrated (Karaganov and Makarov 2015). While figures such as Karaganov continue to influence contemporary debates, the relationship between intellectual traditions and Kremlin policy is neither linear nor deterministic; Moscow selectively draws on these ideas when useful and distances itself when politically expedient (Riehle 2025).

In practice, Russia has cultivated relations across the Asia-Pacific. This engagement is not framed solely through the lens of Sino-Russian cooperation; rather, Moscow seeks to assert its own Asian identity (Kuo 2023). Russia's March 2023 Foreign Policy Concept describes the country as a "Eurasian and Euro-Pacific power." Notably, the document does not treat China and India as partners in its Asia-Pacific policy but instead positions them as key actors within its Eurasian strategy (Administration of the President of the Russian Federation 2019; Kuo 2023). This diverges from Beijing's self-conception—and from widespread international views—that China is a core Asia-Pacific actor. Yet Russia's framing underscores China's growing importance within Eurasia and supports Moscow's strategic pivot eastward, presenting engagement with Asian powers not as a substitute for Europe but as the fulfillment of a distinct Eurasian destiny resistant to Western encroachment (Morozov 2009; Mohapatra 2022).

China's foreign-policy evolution follows a different trajectory but is similarly shaped by historical experience and national identity, blending insecurity rooted in past humiliation with a confident, nationalist drive for status (Callahan 2010). After the Cold War, China's rapid integration into the liberal order forced it to clarify its relationship with the US-led system (Puranen and Chen 2025). As China shifts from a "globalized power" to a "globalizing power" (Denisov, Paramonov, Arapova, and Safranchuk 2021, 80), its diplomacy serves not only economic expansion but also a nationalist project aimed at securing domestic legitimacy and strategic autonomy by constructing a Sinocentric architecture outside Western influence (Zhao 2004). In Eurasia—once peripheral to Chinese strategy—the launch of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) marked a decisive turn toward proactive engagement. Russia's international isolation after the invasion of Ukraine accelerated its eastward pivot, solidifying Central Asia as China's "second region" (Womack 2023) and deepening Moscow's asymmetric dependence on Beijing (Liu 2023).

As this paper will show, numerous sources highlight that the Russia-China relationship is not free of friction (e.g., Swanström 2014; Gabuev 2019; Liu 2023). These tensions complicate—but have not yet

derailed—the broader systemic alignment driven by respective internal thinking of its place in the world, shared anti-hegemonic goals and reinforced by Western sanctions on Russia after 2022. The relationship has evolved from Cold War–era rivalry to a contemporary strategic alignment that increasingly blurs the boundary between the Eurasian and Asia-Pacific theaters (Mayer and Kavalski 2024).

Regarding the term “Asia-Pacific”, it is increasingly being replaced by the more expansive “Indo-Pacific” by countries such as Japan, Australia, and the United States (US). Each of these countries adopts a different geographic conceptualization of the Indo-Pacific region. Recognizing this variation, this paper defines the term Asia-Pacific as a region surrounding the Western Pacific Ocean, whereas the Indo-Pacific is geographically broader, encompassing the Indian Ocean and creating a maritime super-region that links the two oceans. The Indo-Pacific is also a newer term with more strategic meaning advanced by the aforementioned states. Both Russia and China, however, do not welcome the term Indo-Pacific.

The Chinese Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MFA), for example, only began commenting on the Indo-Pacific notion in recent years. Back in 2018, Minister of Foreign Affairs Wang Yi derided the Australian and American preference for calling the region “Indo-Pacific” instead of “Asia-Pacific” as a “headline-grabbing” exercise that would “dissipate like ocean foam” (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People’s Republic of China 2018). Over time, as the PRC appeared to conclude that the concept was here to stay, the MFA began to take the Indo-Pacific strategy more seriously. As a result of the MFA’s reluctance to engage with the concept rhetorically in public, Chinese state media generally refers to the term only when seeking to deny its importance. Chinese foreign policy ideas are usually produced and reproduced in a circular, mutually reinforcing manner from the center (*zhongyang*) down to the scholarly writings published in the public domain. Many of these views are reiterated in Chinese academic journals and policy magazines available on the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) platform. We reviewed these materials but, due to space limitations, selected only a few representative examples to reflect the prevailing perspectives examined in this paper.

This paper asks how and through what forms of coordination Sino-Russian interactions link the Eurasian and Indo-Pacific strategic theaters. This is not intended to be an exercise in empirically testing formal hypotheses. Rather, we trace patterns of cross-theater coordination by drawing on existing academic studies and relevant policy documents in English, Chinese, and translated Russian texts. By connecting two bodies of literature – on Sino-Russian relations in Central Asia and in the Asia-Pacific – we examine how developments in one theater increasingly shape strategic behavior in the other. We do not claim that Sino-Russian alignment is the sole cause of increasing cross-theater interconnection. Rather, we show that intensifying coordination between Moscow and Beijing constitutes a significant reinforcing dynamic linking developments across the two theaters.

While adopting an interpretivist approach, our analysis foregrounds the interaction between systemic pressures, relative material capabilities, and state-level interests in shaping foreign policy behavior. This orientation allows us to interpret observable patterns of Sino-Russian alignment and analyse the responses of smaller states navigating this evolving strategic environment.

In this paper, we conceptualise Sino-Russian alignment not as a formal alliance, but as observable patterns of policy coordination across strategic theaters. Here “alignment” is reflected in three indicators: (1) institutional linkage and coordination, such as the integration or parallel mobilization of regional organisations and joint diplomatic statements; (2) strategic signaling, including coordinated military exercises and public rhetorical positioning in each other’s core regions; and (3) reciprocal diplomatic and geopolitical support that reinforces each state’s regional objectives. These indicators allow us to assess the degree to which developments in Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific are increasingly interconnected through coordinated behavior.

The next section examines Central Asia as a case study to explore Sino-Russian relations within the broader Eurasian context. Despite the PRC's growing dominance in economic and security domains and the underlying tensions in Sino-Russian relations, the two countries do not engage in overt competition in Central Asia. Their relationship, characterized by a blend of cooperation and rivalry, works well in this region. In the third section, we will further demonstrate that this pattern persists and consolidates after Russia's attack on Ukraine in 2022. The fourth section shifts focus to the case study of the Asia-Pacific region to examine Sino-Russian relations in the broader Indo-Pacific context. China plays a crucial role in facilitating Russia's entry into the Asia-Pacific. The fifth section further shows that Moscow's imperative to depend more on China in the Asia-Pacific region becomes prominent after international sanctions against Russia since 2022. The sixth part of this paper compares the varying degrees of agency of several countries amid power competitions in the studied regions.

SINO-RUSSIAN COOPERATION AND COMPETITION IN CENTRAL ASIA

Sino-Russian relations have historically been marked by tensions, with adversarial undercurrents persisting for decades and widely acknowledged in the literature (e.g., Swanström 2014; Gabuev 2019). A longstanding concern is Russia's apprehension regarding Chinese expansion in the Russian Far East (Trenin 2002), recently reaffirmed by a 2025 *New York Times* investigative report (Judah et al. 2025). The report revealed a classified Russian Federal Security Service document detailing deep mistrust of China within Russian intelligence circles, including fears about espionage, territorial encroachments and influence in sensitive regions such as the Arctic and Central Asia – despite the official narrative of an “unshakable” partnership (Judah et al. 2025). Further frictions stem from an entrenched Russian perception of China as the subordinate partner in the relationship, now accompanied by anxiety over a reversal of this hierarchy (Gabuev 2019; Liu 2023). As China's presence grows in Russia's traditional sphere of influence, especially Central Asia, Moscow's unease has intensified. Even oil price negotiations between the two sides have revealed underlying tensions (Liu 2023).¹ Russian elites have voiced public concern over excessive dependence on China (Varga 2025; Bogusz and Rodkiewicz 2025). These issues underscore enduring fragilities in the relationship. Nevertheless, such divides have been gradually tempered by expanding bilateral cooperation and Russia's increasing reliance on China following international sanctions imposed in 2022 (Liu 2023; Sagild and Hsiung 2024).

In the context of Central Asia, it is important to note that the region has had historical ties to China that predate the founding of the People's Republic. Most pertinent to the focus of this paper is Beijing's relations with Central Asian states after they obtained independence in 1991. Since then, China has worked with Central Asian states primarily on security and economic issues (Chen 2015; Umarov 2021). Concerning security, Beijing sought to resolve border disputes and prevent separatist movements, particularly secessionist attempts by what the Chinese government considers Uyghur separatists in China's Xinjiang region. This security cooperation was institutionalized with the establishment of the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) in 2001 (Chen 2014). Beijing's economic interest in Central Asia centers on accessing the region's natural resources to fuel Chinese growth, exporting consumer goods to Central Asian markets, and using Central Asia as a transit route to connect Eurasia with China's key trading partners in South Asia, the Middle East, and Europe. Over the decades, formal and informal interactions between China and Central Asia have proliferated, particularly in the economic sphere.

¹ We lack detailed information about China's negotiations with Russia regarding oil prices. However, Saunder and Stevens (2024) conservatively estimate that between March 2022 and June 2024, China saved at least US\$16 billion by purchasing discounted Russian oil. This represents a significant advantage at a time when China is experiencing decelerating growth.

Although China has become a prominent economic pillar for Central Asian countries, Russia still maintains significant economic ties, rooted in its longstanding presence in the region.

In the Xi Jinping era, China has adopted a more proactive diplomatic posture, aiming for greater strategic autonomy and flexibility in regions such as Central Asia. This proactive diplomacy in Central Asia and various parts of the world is vital for the internal construction of a powerful, modern Chinese nation-state, a topic that has been explored by other scholars (Zhao 2004; Callahan 2010). For instance, in recent years, China has not only engaged in security cooperation through multilateral platforms such as the SCO but has also sought to expand its independent security cooperation in the region, without Russia. One notable example is Tajikistan's hosting of a Chinese paramilitary base on its territory (Jardine and Lemon 2020; Umarov 2021).

Despite China's rising security presence in Central Asia, Beijing seeks to reassure Moscow that its regional engagement is driven solely by China's domestic security imperatives rather than any challenge to Russia's traditional security role. These security concerns include curbing potential links between Uyghur separatists and their Central Asian counterparts and containing the spillover of instability from Afghanistan or other nearby conflict zones. China has generally avoided encroaching on Russia's established sphere of influence, particularly in the security domain. A notable example is the 2022 unrest in Kazakhstan, where Russia intervened under the auspices of the Collective Security Treaty Organization (CSTO). China respected this move, offering rhetorical support and indicating that, if necessary, it would back both Kazakhstan and Russia through the SCO framework. Beijing's limited experience with military operations in the region, combined with its cautious posture, has kept it from overstepping Moscow's role as Central Asia's principal security guarantor (Chen 2023).

For Moscow, as long as Beijing respects Russia's security role in Central Asia and allows it to remain the region's primary arms supplier, it is unlikely to respond negatively to China's security arrangements with different Central Asian countries. This tacit understanding has enabled pragmatic coordination between the two powers, allowing them to carve out their areas of influence in Central Asia without provoking serious competition.

As both China and Russia face intensifying competition from the US, they view Central Asia as a region where they can avoid conflicts, cooperate to some extent, and exclude American influence. China and Russia's mutual interest in maintaining authoritarianism globally, along with their support for autocratic regimes in Central Asia, aligns closely with the interests of regional leaders. For example, following the US withdrawal from Afghanistan in 2021, Central Asian states did not renew their agreements to allow continued US military presence. This reminds us that while the preceding analysis primarily focuses on the strategic calculations and interests of Moscow and Beijing, Central Asian countries can exercise agency in navigating the international environment to preserve their own strategic autonomy. Although the specific hedging behaviors of these states will be examined in depth in a later section of this paper, the immediate context of their regional environment has been shifted by recent war in Ukraine. Before addressing that agency, hence, the following section evaluates the geopolitical situation in Central Asia following Russia's attack on Ukraine in 2022, exploring how this milestone has reinforced the established patterns of Sino-Russian coordination.

SINO-RUSSIAN ALIGNMENT IN CENTRAL ASIA AFTER 2022

Russia's attack on Ukraine has raised concerns among Central Asian countries, prompting them to tactfully engage China as a counterbalance to their traditional relations with the Kremlin. With Moscow preoccupied by the war, China has progressively expanded its economic influence in the region. For example, Chinese state-owned enterprises have deepened cooperation with Central Asian states to secure energy supplies (Khassenkhanova 2025). The China-Central Asia Gas Pipeline, which runs through

Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and into China, bypassing Russia, exemplifies how Beijing has seized the opportunity created by the 2022 war to bolster regional energy security.

Moreover, China and Central Asian states share a common interest in developing alternative transport routes that circumvent Russia, ensuring the security of trade between China and Europe. Kazakhstan, which has spent over a decade positioning itself as a key Eurasian transit hub, currently leads the region's transit sector. Its strategic position has been reinforced by the Trans-Caspian International Transport Route, also known as the Middle Corridor, whose significance has grown markedly since 2022. Today, approximately 85% of the goods transported from China to the European Union (EU) pass through Kazakhstan. To remain competitive in this evolving landscape, other Central Asian countries will need to improve their infrastructure and attract greater investment.

Despite China's growing visibility in Central Asia since 2022, Moscow continues to cooperate with Beijing, as Western sanctions have increased Russia's reliance on China. While it remains unclear whether China was aware of Russia's intent to invade Ukraine in early 2022, what is evident is the significance of the joint Sino-Russian statement declaring a "no limits" partnership, issued just days before the war (State Council of the People's Republic of China 2022). In May 2024, the two sides released another joint statement, on "deepening China-Russia comprehensive strategic partnership of coordination for a new era on the occasion of the 75th anniversary of the establishment of diplomatic ties between the two countries" (The National Committee of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Committee 2024). At the same time, however, Beijing has reiterated its support for Kazakhstan's territorial integrity, sovereignty, and independence – a subtle signal to Moscow not to invade Kazakhstan as it did with Ukraine (Sciorati and Silvan 2023, 53; Bartlett 2022).

Hence, the relationship between the dragon and the bear remains characterized by a delicate balance of strategic cooperation and competition. US influence in the region is waning, and both the US and the EU are preoccupied with the Ukrainian crisis, Middle Eastern conflicts, and internal challenges such as inflation (Wong and Akylbayev 2022). American and European policymakers have sometimes optimistically assumed that China and Russia would not maintain a strong relationship or compete too fiercely to cooperate. These views are reflected in policy papers, public debates, and commentaries (Energy Intelligence Group 2024; Foreign Policy Research Institute 2024). Accordingly, Western policymakers, have not responded in a timely or effective manner to the growing ties between Russia and China in Central Asia.

As noted at the outset of this paper, Russia has officially acknowledged China is a key partner in the Eurasian space. While their historical rivalry and mutual distrust offer grounds for skepticism, both states have demonstrated a willingness to set aside these tensions to harness their collective power for their shared national interests and preferences for the international order. China and Russia both conceive of themselves as civilizational states, each with distinct traditions to offer the world, offering an attractive alternative pole of power to states disillusioned with the US-led liberal international order (Laine and Komin 2025; Shakhanova 2024). With their significant economic power (especially China) and political power (e.g., both possess nuclear weapons and permanent seats in the UN Security Council), their desire to align themselves more closely is strong. Central Asia serves as a strategic location to showcase their solidarity. This high-level geopolitical convergence is sometimes underappreciated in the West due to the belief that the two countries compete over certain sectors in Central Asia.

Take the SCO, for instance. Western observers often question, and at times, harshly criticize, the SCO's effectiveness, particularly during high-profile summits involving Xi, Putin, and other member-state leaders, even in the post-2022 period (Legieć 2021; Umarov 2024). Yet what is often overlooked is that, despite the SCO not functioning as efficiently as China might have hoped, its symbolic value is crucial for both China and Russia. In other words, *an organization that does not function well can still be valuable for China and Russia* if it serves as a platform to showcase goodwill and cooperation among

its members. Relationship management is central to Chinese political culture. In this light, the SCO can be seen as a vehicle through which China seeks to socialize Russia and Central Asian countries – fostering mutual trust, coordination, and reciprocity (Shakhanova 2024). As Yuan (2023) rightly argues, China uses the SCO to coordinate with Russia in countering US activities and preventing Washington from projecting and entrenching its presence in the region. At the same time, Beijing uses the SCO to address Russian concerns about growing Chinese influence. Yuan (2023) calls this an “institutional balancing strategy”, whereby the SCO simultaneously excludes US influence while reassuring Russia of its continued role in regional affairs.

Moreover, China supports Russia’s efforts to cultivate a Greater Eurasia identity and foreign policy agenda that serves its national interests. At the core of this identity lies a shared vision of a non-Western space in which both powers can advance their preferred political, economic, and security order. This explains their attempts to link institutions such as the SCO, CSTO, BRI, and the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU) into a coherent Greater Eurasian community (Ekaterina and Chen 2022; Yuan 2023). China and Russia issued the “Joint Statement between the People’s Republic of China and the Russian Federation on Cooperation in the Construction of the Silk Road Economic Belt and the Eurasian Economic Union” in 2015. Since then, there has been a notable surge in news coverage regarding China and Russia’s cooperation and willingness to link up the BRI with the EAEU across various Eurasian nations that are both members of the EAEU and participants in the BRI. This rise in reporting reflects the growing visibility of collaborative efforts (Kuteleva and Vasiliev 2021; Van Noort and Chatterjee-Dooddy 2023; Li 2023; Liu 2023; Pei and Zhang 2024; Zhang and Yang 2025).

However, heightened media attention does not necessarily imply that local populations regard China and Russia in an entirely favourable light (Chen and Günther 2020; Nuriddenova 2025). Nor does increased coverage indicate a seamless synergy between the BRI and EAEU. Even some Chinese scholars (e.g., Han 2019; Pei and Zhang 2024) have acknowledged persistent coordination challenges. Han (2019), for example, argues that the lack of financing mechanisms within the SCO constrains its ability to meet member states’ growing demands, limiting effective cooperation between the SCO, the BRI, and the EAEU. Furthermore, the protectionist measures for the EAEU’s internal market have created reluctance to establish a free trade zone with China, impeding deeper collaboration between the EAEU and the BRI (Han 2019). Similarly, Pei and Zhang’s (2024) study of the Madrid-Yiwu train, which aims to link BRI countries from China through Eurasia to Europe, highlights how uneven infrastructure development within the EAEU continues to disrupt efficient operations.

One could also argue, perhaps cynically, that Russia and China pursue different priorities in their efforts at synergy, resulting in limited practical integration. Russia may continue to privilege its own institutions, such as the CSTO and the EAEU, or attempt to co-opt the BRI into its vision of a Greater Eurasian Partnership. Moreover, Moscow’s engagement in the SCO may be largely symbolic. These dynamics are not lost on Beijing. China appears untroubled by the structural and strategic mismatches between the two sides. What matters for China are the symbolic and performative dimensions of Sino-Russian presence in Central Asia, which serve to legitimize China’s ongoing operations and growing influence in the region.

In 2017, the SCO formally admitted two new full members: India and Pakistan. While some may interpret the expansion as a Chinese strategy to dilute Russian influence within the organization, in reality, Russia has actively supported India’s accession—a move that also aligns with Beijing’s broader strategic interests. India is geographically proximate to Eurasia and plays a key role in the US-led Indo-Pacific initiatives. India’s inclusion brings New Delhi closer to the rules and norms of the SCO, which diverge considerably from those of the Western liberal order (Yuan 2023). Beyond the SCO, China and Russia have also involved India in the BRICS group and the Russia-India-China trilateral framework to discuss issues of common concern (Melvin 2021; Mohapatra 2022).

The Russia-China-India framework was created by former Russian prime minister Yevgeny Primakov (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation 2023). Although the format lost momentum with the rise of the BRICS grouping, Russia has sought to revive the trilateral dialogue following its invasion of Ukraine (Laine and Komin 2025). This revival is part of Russia's broader strategy for full-spectrum engagement with the Global South to counter US hegemony, a vision shared by China. Moscow positions itself as a mediator between China and India, aiming to ease bilateral tensions, provide them with more points of contact, and limit India's alignment with the US-led Indo-Pacific alliances (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Russian Federation 2023). The interplay between the Eurasian and Indo-Pacific strategic theaters is clearly visible in this context.

The SCO's recent enlargement with Iran joining in 2023 and Belarus in 2024, has extended the organization's reach into the Greater Middle East and enhanced its geopolitical breadth. These developments illustrate Sino-Russian alignment is not only ideological but also material, as both states mobilize resources to attract like-minded players. In doing so, they seek to constrain US influence across the Eurasian landmass, the Indo-Pacific, and potentially the Greater Middle East. Ultimately, the strengthening of institutional and symbolic ties in Central Asia serves as a blueprint for Sino-Russian coordination, setting the stage for an examination of how these dynamics extend into Russia's historical and evolving interests within the broader Asia-Pacific theater in the next section.

RUSSIA'S ASIA-PACIFIC INTEREST BEFORE 2022 AND WHY CHINA MATTERS

As noted above, Russia's engagement with Asia transcends policy decisions and is deeply rooted in questions of national identity (Neumann 2017; Wishnick 2017, 122; Kolosov 2003; Lotman 2002; Laruelle 2009; Morozov 2009). The notions of "the West", "Europe", and "the East" are not understood or interpreted by Russians in a uniform manner (Morozov 2009). Russia's foreign policy orientation has long reflected internal debates between Westernizing impulses and Slavophile or later Eurasianist visions of national identity. While certain rulers such as Peter the Great, Alexander II and Gorbachev, pursued selective Westernization, Russia as a state has never consistently aspired to be part of the West. Rather, it has historically sought to assert its distinctiveness and demand recognition as a great power on its own terms. Among some elites, forging closer ties with rising Asian powers like China serves as a way to reassert Russia's strategic autonomy and global status. For example, during his tenure as foreign minister, Yevgeny Primakov saw partnership with China as a means of counterbalancing US dominance and resisting Western encroachment (Curanović 2012).

Russia has actively sought to engage with Asia, becoming increasingly involved in Asian diplomacy since the early 21st century (Mohapatra 2022). This Asian or Asia-Pacific dimension is vital for Russia to rationalize the "Asian" component of its Eurasian identity, justify its presence along the Pacific Ocean coastline, and to position itself as a bridge between East and West (Wishnick 2017, 122-3). This dual identity reinforces Russia's claim to great power status by highlighting its influence across both Europe and Asia (Wishnick 2017, 123). Under Vladimir Putin's leadership, Russia has intensified its diplomatic outreach to the East. Development of the Far East and Siberia has facilitated ties with the Asia-Pacific. After the 2008 global financial crisis (GFC), amid perceptions of Western decline, Russia began shifting its energy strategy toward Asia to reduce reliance on European markets. In 2009, it completed the Eastern Siberian-Pacific Ocean pipeline, expanding energy exports not only to China and Japan but also to Southeast Asian countries such as Indonesia and the Philippines (Wishnick 2017, 124).

Another repercussion from the GFC was a renewed push by Vladimir Putin and former Kazakhstani president Nursultan Nazarbayev to establish the Eurasian Economic Union (EAEU), aimed at fostering greater regional integration. This union officially came into effect in 2015. Both leaders envisioned regional integration as a stepping stone for collectively enhancing their international status and influence

within global governance structures (Putin 2011). A key factor underpinning the EAEU's presumed connectivity advantage was Russia's geographic position and its ties to Asia. Given that most Central Asian states are landlocked, the appeal of joining an isolationist bloc would have been limited. Russia, as the only member with direct maritime access, was expected to facilitate access to global markets. This rationale also reinforced Russia's broader pivot to Asia under its "Greater Eurasia" vision (Administration of the President of the Russian Federation 2019).

However, in practice, Moscow has used the EAEU to advance its political objectives, such as enhancing its status as a great power, rather than committing to genuine economic integration. Protectionist policies and limited financial resources continue to undermine the EAEU's cohesion. The most effective aspect of the union seems to be its labor market, which allows citizens from member states to work legally in Russia (Silvan and Kaczmarek 2022). Since Russia's invasion of Ukraine in 2022 and the imposition of sweeping sanctions, transit through Russian territory has become increasingly impractical (Silvan and Kaczmarek 2022), and the appeal of the Russian labor market has also diminished as many Central Asians have begun leaving Russia (Rickeleton 2025).

Even before 2022, China has played a pivotal role in Russia's turn towards the Asia-Pacific region. China's endorsement is key to Russia's acceptance as a legitimate actor in the Asia-Pacific, despite reluctance from Japan and the US. This endorsement is evident in China's support for Russia's participation in the ASEAN Regional Forum (ARF) and the Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) (Bilveer 1998, 496; Melvin 2021). However, China's support alone does not guarantee Russia's integration into the Asia-Pacific. Regional players have the power to determine Russia's participation in regional activities. Russia's involvement in ASEAN activities, for example, is contingent upon Moscow's acknowledgement of ASEAN's leading role in maintaining peace and stability in the region. In 2012, Russia hosted the APEC summit in Vladivostok, where Putin declared Russia as an integral part of the Asia-Pacific region (Kremlin 2012).

In addition to its alignment with China, Russia had, prior to 2022, cultivated ties with Japan, North Korea, South Korea, and several South Asian and Southeast Asian countries (Kashin 2014; Melvin 2021). These engagements are framed by Moscow as part of its "Greater Eurasian Partnership" (President of Russia Website 2016; Mohapatra 2022) and have involved the development of distinct economic and security policies toward multiple Asia-Pacific states. The emphasis has generally been on economic cooperation — particularly in the arms and energy sectors — with comparatively less focus on security and geopolitical issues. Prior to Putin's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, trade relations with South Korea were flourishing, and Japan remained open to dialogue with Moscow over territorial disputes and the deepening of economic ties (Rozman 2025).

A 2025 report by the US-based Foreign Policy Research Institute rightly observes that Russia is playing a two-level game. At the systemic level, Russia engages in systemic balancing by aligning with China to counter the US and the broader West. At the regional level in the Indo-Pacific, however, it employs hedging strategies to diversify its relationships, including outreach to China's actual or potential rivals, while "avoid[ing] explicitly taking one side at the obvious expense of another in regional disputes" (Foreign Policy Research Institute 2025). The 2022 invasion of Ukraine, however, has strained Russia's ties with several regional players and significantly increased its dependence on China. Before examining this growing asymmetry in the next section, we turn to Vietnam as a case that illustrates Russia's ongoing attempt to navigate this two-level strategic game.

In the territorial dispute between China and several claimant countries in the South China Sea, Russia has maintained a stance of non-involvement. Although Vietnam and China are opponents in these disputes, Russia and Vietnam have a deeply rooted cooperative relationship, with Russia being the main arms supplier for Vietnam (Storey 2021). One might expect a confrontation because of the differences between Russia and China on the South China Sea issue, but beyond Moscow's rhetorical neutrality on

the issue, Russia's behavior has often appeared to support China. For instance, when an international tribunal denied Beijing's South China Sea claims in 2016, Russia supported the notion that disputes should be resolved by the parties involved without external interference. Russia agreed, to some extent, with China's refusal to accept the ruling, arguing that China had not been a party to the proceedings and its stance had not been heard by the tribunal. However, this does not mean that Russia supports China's territorial claims (Dikarev and Lukin 2022), but from an outsider's perspective, Russia is still seen as pro-Chinese on this matter despite its proclaimed neutrality.

After the tribunal ruling in 2016, China and Russia conducted combined naval exercises in the South China Sea. In 2017, they further demonstrated their military cooperation with joint naval drills in the Baltic Sea. Experts interpret these joint exercises as mutual support for each other's regional interests (Storey 2021,7). This collaboration highlights the reciprocal nature of Moscow and Beijing's relationship. Notably, the fact that their drills took place in undisputed areas of the South China Sea suggests that Russia was careful not to jeopardize its ties with other Southeast Asian countries while cooperating with China. The performative elements of China and Russia's joint naval drills hint at future coordination between the two nations from the Indo-Pacific to the Eurasian space. Although Russia has long sought to assert its own Asian identity and bridge East and West, its entry into this theater has increasingly relied on Chinese endorsement, a dynamic that has transitioned from mutual benefit into a profound strategic dependency following the international fallout of the 2022 invasion of Ukraine, which we will explore in the next section.

GROWING RUSSIAN DEPENDENCE ON CHINA IN THE ASIA-PACIFIC SINCE 2022

Following the 2022 Russo-Ukrainian war, Putin effectively forfeited the opportunity to foster better relations with key Indo-Pacific players such as Japan and South Korea, choosing instead to deepen Russia's alignment not only with China, but also with North Korea (Rozman 2025). By contributing to Russia's war fighting capabilities in increasingly direct ways, Pyongyang strategically reinforces the Sino-Russian alignment in its opposition to Western influence and goal of disrupting the US-led international order. North Korea's expanding military cooperation with Russia further strengthens the perception that Moscow and Beijing can rely on regional partners to defy Western pressure, thereby advancing the multipolar world order that both states seek to establish (Stewart and Shin 2024; Ghiasy, Chen and Panda 2025).

The 2022 Russo-Ukrainian war did not fundamentally alter the established dynamic in which China remains a dominant player in the Asia-Pacific, while Russia, though less influential, retains a meaningful presence through arm sales and energy cooperation. What the war did shift, however, was Russia's relationship with two crucial players in Northeast Asia – Japan and South Korea – both of which have imposed sanctions on Moscow and have become more assertive in their support for Ukraine (Corbin 2024). Tokyo and Seoul's hard stance on Russia is driven less by US pressure and more by national concerns over the implications of an emboldened China or North Korea, which could destabilize the regional security environment (Brown 2024). In Sagild and Hsiung's (2024) analysis of Chinese scholarly discourses, many PRC analysts believe that Moscow needs to align more closely with China to secure its backing regarding Ukraine and its standing in the Asia-Pacific region. In exchange, Russia is expected to refrain from sanctioning China or condemning its actions in a potential Taiwan crisis, while continuing to supply energy to China (Sagild and Hsiung 2024). Thus, contrary to the views of some Western experts, the Sino-Russian strategic partnership appears to be more resilient than fragile (Sagild and Hsiung 2024)

In Southeast Asia, Russia's position appears more favorable than in Northeast Asia. Several ASEAN countries including Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Vietnam, as well as American treaty allies the

Philippines and Thailand, chose not to impose sanctions on Russia (Grossman 2022). This has created a stronger incentive for Russia to deepen its engagement with the region. Back in 2015, the Russia-led EAEU signed its inaugural Free Trade Agreement (FTA) with Vietnam, making Vietnam the first ASEAN member to formalize such an agreement with the EAEU. According to Novikova and Nguyen (2024), by the end of 2023, trade volume between Vietnam and Russia had increased by 64% compared to pre-FTA levels — rising from US\$2.2 billion in 2015 to US\$3.6 billion.²

China has long held a dominant presence in the Asia-Pacific, and Russia’s growing ties with select Southeast Asian states pose no real challenge to its position. The dragon and the bear continue to find strategic value in managing potential frictions while presenting a united front against the US-led alliance architecture in the region. From Eurasia to the Indo-Pacific, some observers frame Sino-Russian alignment as “strategic partners”, “axis of convenience”, or “Russia the junior partner and China the senior one” (Melvin 2021). Setting aside these bumper sticker labels, the more important point is that both countries increasingly complement one another in their shared efforts to counter the Western liberal international order. Economically, Russia appears to be the junior partner, particularly given its growing dependence on China in both Central Asia and the Asia-Pacific. However, Russia’s initiation of a full-scale conventional war against Ukraine, in contrast to China’s preference for strategic ambiguity, complicates any straightforward hierarchical classification.

The implications of this alignment are particularly significant for European policymakers. Europe can no longer concentrate solely on security challenges within Eastern Europe. The areas of concern now extend from “a north-south gradient across the landmass of Eastern Europe to a southwest and northeast gradient from the South China Sea to the Korean Peninsula,” as Mayer and Kavalski’s 2024 commentary in *The Diplomat* suggests. Although China may reject direct comparisons between Ukraine and Taiwan crises, strategic connections between these theaters are becoming increasingly evident, despite their differing contexts. Josef Borrell (2024), former High Representative of the EU for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy, acknowledged this connection in the EU’s publication in late 2024.

Back in 2024, China increasingly appeared willing to sacrifice aspects of its relationship with Europe to strengthen its cooperation with Russia in opposing the US-led world order. In July 2024, Chinese troops conducted a joint military exercise with Belarus near Poland, a member of both the EU and North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO). This marked the first China-Belarus joint exercise held in Europe, conducted under the pretext of counterterrorism shortly after Belarus joined the SCO in 2024 (Karmanau 2024). This development highlights the burgeoning Sino-Russian alignment in the Eurasian space and sent an unmistakable signal to Europe that its security architecture is under pressure. While the likelihood of China waging a war in Europe remains low, the performative dimension of this joint exercise is undeniable. Despite efforts by European leaders to persuade Beijing to withdraw its support for Russia and support efforts to end the war in Ukraine, China has continued to strengthen its strategic partnership with Russia (Agence France-Presse 2024).

Without Russia’s endorsement, it is unlikely that China would have been able to conduct joint military drills with Belarus on European soil. The same logic applies to the Asia-Pacific theater – without China’s tacit approval, Putin’s visits to both North Korea and Vietnam in June 2024, just one month before the Sino-Belarusian exercise in Europe, would have been diplomatically more difficult to carry out.

² According to Novikova and Nguyen (2024), from 2015 to 2023, Vietnam’s exports to Russia reached US\$1.7 billion, reflecting a 20% increase, while imports from Russia totalled US\$ 1.88 billion—a threefold increase over the same period. It is important to note, however, that not all EAEU countries have experienced a similarly steady rise in trade turnover with Vietnam.

In a previous section, we have noted China and Russia's significant realignment in Central Asia. As a summary, here we compare the pre-2022 and post-2022 transformations in both the Eurasian and the Asia-Pacific theaters. Before and after 2022, Sino-Russian alignment's major transformation can be seen in economic, security, political, and the less visible but nevertheless real identity domains. In the economic domain, Sino-Russian alignment transforms from frictional coordination to asymmetric economic dependency. Before 2022, we can see that the economic relationship was characterized by underlying tensions, such as friction over oil prices and Russian anxiety regarding China's expansion into its traditional sphere of influence. But post-2022, Western sanctions have transformed Russia's reliance on China from a strategic choice into a survival necessity. Also, the EAEU was once a vehicle for Russian status; its appeal has diminished since 2022 as transit through Russia has become impractical, forcing a closer, albeit subordinate, link to China's BRI.

In the security domain, Sino-Russian relations have moved from local coordination to a global performative alignment that links Europe and the Indo-Pacific through cross-border signaling. The unprecedented joint exercises, such as the July 2024 China-Belarus drill near the Polish border, are not just about the stated intent of counter-terrorism exercises, but they are symbolic and performative signal that the security architectures of Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific are linked.

In the political and diplomatic domain, we see a new level of reciprocal diplomatic support; for example, Putin's high-profile visits to North Korea and Vietnam were likely facilitated by China's tacit approval. Furthermore, there is SCO expansion and the deepening of the Russia-China-North Korea nexus. Lastly, in the identity domain, which is connected to realpolitik changes, we observe a Russia that once sought to be a bridge between East and West on its own terms; its Asian identity is now filtered more through its coordination with Beijing.

As the Sino-Russian alignment tightens different strategic theaters, the regional states caught between these powers must adapt their own strategies to survive, as explored in the following discussion on smaller state agency.

COUNTRIES' AGENCY AMID SINO-RUSSIAN ALIGNMENT POST-2022

The IR literature offers varying definitions of balancing, bandwagoning, and hedging. While scholars may not agree on how these terms should be conceptualized (e.g., Lake 1996; He, 2008; Kang 2003/4), our aim is not to intervene in these debates or propose new definitions. Rather, we employ these terms to highlight the agency of Central Asian and Asia-Pacific countries and to identify their strategic orientations. According to balance of power theory, states are expected to form "firm alignments", either by balancing against or bandwagoning with revisionist powers such as Russia and China (Marston 2024). In practice, however, most states in Central Asia and the Asia-Pacific appear to be pursuing hedging strategies.

Hedging, by definition, lies between balancing and bandwagoning, incorporating elements of both (Dikarev and Lukin 2022). It is essentially a "risk management strategy" that signals "ambiguity to competing powers in order to preserve strategic autonomy" (Marston 2024). Hedging tends to be adopted as a strategy in response to geostrategic uncertainty. In the case of the Asia-Pacific, this uncertainty stems from the US-China rivalry and the range of possible regional futures it entails, including Chinese hegemony, a potential US withdrawal or broader instability (Marston 2024). In Central Asia, uncertainty is driven by both Russia and China's influence – two powerful neighbors that elicit caution from the region's relatively weak and recently independent states. Smaller states may favor hedging to avoid overdependence on any single power or being locked into potentially costly or risky alliances and benefit economically from relationships with multiple powers.

The exact terminology for hedging strategies varies by regions: in Central Asia, it is referred to as a multivector policy, while in Southeast Asia, it is known as a multidirectional policy. Despite these semantic differences, the underlying logic remains the same: to diversify relations in order to navigate great power competition. Importantly, such strategies were in place well before the geopolitical disruptions of 2022. The Russo-Ukrainian war did not change the nature of Central Asian and Southeast Asian countries' diversification efforts. Starting with Central Asia, Russia and China remain key pillars in the multivector policies pursued by states in the region. Prominent Japan-based Uzbek researcher, Timur Dadabaev (2024, 5-6) argues that strategic competition in Central Asia underscores the need for external actors to provide alternatives to Central Asian states. Dadabaev (2024: 9) further suggests that the US and Japan, with their converging interests in the region, should coordinate their Central Asia policy through a decolonial lens, that is, aiming to "... decolonize these countries' ties with Russia and possibly China". Kazakhstan has greater flexibility to hedge, balancing relations with Russia, China, and other external powers. While it is deeply involved in China's BRI and Russia's CSTO, Kazakhstan has also signed a strategic partnership agreement with the EU on raw materials and is attempting to develop alternative oil routes, such as via the Caspian Sea and Azerbaijan to Europe to reduce dependency on Russian routes. In contrast, the weaker states of Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan are mostly subject to Russian and Chinese influences. Overall, Central Asian states are landlocked, share borders with both Russia and China and rely heavily on both countries for energy exports and infrastructure development. This reliance results in limited hedging options for Central Asian states compared to Asia-Pacific countries.

In the Asia-Pacific, the development of Southeast Asia's strategic posture is worth noting. Both the Chinese and US vectors are strong, even during the Second Trump era, despite the region's diverse array of external relations. If anything, these countries have intensified their hedging strategies to signal ambiguity to major powers, projecting neutrality amid intensifying geopolitical conflicts (Myers 2024). As an example of hedging, the case of Vietnam is illustrative. Vietnam increasingly engages in economic cooperation with both China and the US. The first Vietnam-US Economic Dialogue was held in Washington, D.C. in June 2024. Hanoi pursues security and diplomatic cooperation with China while also participating in defense cooperation with the US and its allies. In response to the rising tensions in the South China Sea, Vietnam sought to improve its military capabilities by fully participating in the Rim of the Pacific Exercise (RIMPAC), a biennial event hosted by the US Navy's Indo-Pacific Command that takes place in the waters in and around the Hawaiian Islands, for the first time in 2018 (Parameswaran 2018).³ Nonetheless, Vietnam's hedging strategy is not straightforward and requires careful calibration. Vietnam chose not to participate in RIMPAC 2022 and cancelled two scheduled port calls by US aircraft carriers. This decision was reportedly due to concerns about a potential PRC attack on Taiwan. Given the intensifying China-US competition, Vietnam's leadership may have felt it necessary to avoid actions that could be perceived as aligning too closely with the US against China (Vu 2023).

This nuanced approach is further reflected in Vietnam's broader maritime cooperation strategy. For example, Vietnam has developed security ties with India and Japan. India has provided Vietnam with defense support, including a US\$100 million credit line for patrol boats and US\$500 million for larger defense procurement, along with regular bilateral maritime exercises and port visits (Vu 2023). Similarly, Japan has supplied Vietnam with patrol vessels and funding for a satellite-based surveillance system, enhancing Vietnam's maritime domain awareness and law enforcement capabilities (Vu 2023). Pursuing defense cooperation with partners of the US, notably Japan, is seen as a safer strategy than direct extensive military collaboration with the US. This cautious approach avoids provoking China while still

³ Several other Southeast Asian states have also participated in RIMPAC including Brunei, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Thailand.

bolstering Vietnam's defense capabilities through reliable partners. Vietnam's hedging strategy entails a balancing act of engaging multiple great powers to maximize security and economic gains, while preserving strategic autonomy and avoiding direct confrontation with China.

Weak states may sometimes have more limited room to hedge. For instance, Cambodia, Laos, and Myanmar are generally under China's influence, maintain cordial relations with Russia, and overall fall within the orbit of Sino-Russian alignment (Storey 2021; Chen, Taylor, Gerstl, and Kironka 2025). Despite this, the Russo-Ukrainian war shows that even weaker states can exercise their agency in navigating great power competition. Notably, Cambodia adopted an unexpectedly firm stance against Russia's actions, influenced by its historical experience of occupation by Vietnam (Sochan 2024). Yet Cambodia's approach has not been uniform. When it held the ASEAN chairmanship, the bloc adopted a more moderate stance, urging restraint and dialogue without specifically addressing Russia's role in the invasion. Thus, Cambodia has acted differently as an individual state and as ASEAN chair. Despite these positions, Phnom Penh maintains it has a close relationship with Moscow, with both sides committed to improving their relations (Sochan 2024).

Lastly, both regionalism and regional integration efforts are evident in Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific. These groupings reflect efforts by regional countries to proactively strengthen their autonomy in navigating great power competition. The logic behind such regionalism is also hedging in nature, seeking to diversify risks associated with over-reliance on China and Russia.

Different hedging strategies shape the dynamics of Sino-Russian alignment in distinct ways and carry varied implications for how the boundaries between the Eurasian and Asia-Pacific strategic theaters are drawn. That is essentially a separate research project extending beyond what this paper can reasonably cover. As noted, some weaker states—Myanmar, for example—may increasingly gravitate toward the emerging Sino-Russian bloc or adopt behaviors that tacitly accommodate it. Yet other hedging strategies can complicate or even undermine the conditions for Sino-Russian coordination when states are unwilling to commit fully to any major power. Bomassi's 2025 analysis illustrates this well, highlighting Indo-Pacific cases (e.g., Indonesia) where deliberate ambiguity has constrained the effectiveness of Sino-Russian cooperation. The diverse hedging strategies employed by states across Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific underscore the far-reaching impact of the Sino-Russian alignment, leading to broader conclusions regarding the future of the international order in the next section.

CONCLUSIONS

If current trends persist, a more united Sino-Russian front may emerge, spanning Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific as a significant counterweight to the liberal international order. While both Moscow and Beijing describe this relationship as a "comprehensive strategic partnership of coordination," they deliberately avoid framing it as a formal military-political alliance, preferring a fluid and flexible arrangement that avoids entanglement in each other's direct military conflicts (The Embassy of the Russian Federation to the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland 2021; Melvin 2021). Despite the symbolic nature of many joint military drills, this alignment nonetheless constitutes a consequential geopolitical development that links once-distinct strategic theaters.

The 2022 Russo-Ukrainian war has served as a critical catalyst in this process, deepening Russia's material and diplomatic dependency on China while forcing Moscow to align more closely with Beijing's vision for the Asia-Pacific. This coordination is evidenced by strategic signaling, such as joint exercises in Europe and the Asia-Pacific, and the mobilization of regional organizations like the SCO to showcase solidarity and exclude external influences. These developments suggest that the security architectures of

Eurasia and the Indo-Pacific are now inextricably linked, with developments in one region having immediate implications for the other.

Amidst this intensifying great power alignment, the agency of smaller states remains a pivotal factor in the regional order. Countries across Central Asia and the Asia-Pacific continue to employ hedging strategies to preserve their strategic autonomy and avoid overdependence on any single power. While some weaker states may gravitate toward the emerging Sino-Russian bloc, others continue to seek diverse external relations to maximize their survival and economic prospects.

Ultimately, the growing interconnectedness of these theaters reflects a broader shift toward a multipolar world order characterized by a non-Western space where Moscow and Beijing can advance their preferred political and security norms. To fully grasp the extent of this transformation, future research must look beyond Central Asia and the Asia-Pacific to examine how the Greater Middle East, South Asia, and the Western Indian Ocean are being integrated into these evolving strategic theaters. In addition, conclusive measurement of hedging strategies' impacts on Sino-Russian alignment in different strategic theaters should be explored in future studies.

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